

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF NCC-FOAM

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ABSTRACT

Today's society is a society in constant motion with a strong focus on rapid development. The desire for rapid development and continuous growth causes Earth's resources to be consumed in an increasingly fast pace. Constituents in conventional fibre-reinforced composite sandwich structures which are widely used in marine applications, sports, aerospace and construction, such as carbon fibre, polyester, vinyl ester, epoxy resins, PVC- and PET foam are usually oil-based. It is therefore of great importance for our society that we are trying to replace these petroleum-based products with bio-based equivalents derived from renewable CO₂-neutral plants.

Cellulose, the primary structural component of plants, is the most ubiquitous and abundant organic compound on the planet. When cellulose fibrils are processed under carefully controlled conditions, it is possible to release highly crystalline nano-particles known as "nano crystalline cellulose (NCC)". NCC has some very interesting mechanical properties: a single NCC fibre typically has a Young's modulus of around 150 GPa and a strength of 10 GPa.

MELODEA and the Hebrew University of Jerusalem recently developed a unique technique for self-assembling NCC into highly ordered layered cellular structures, i.e. foams, for use as lightweight core materials for biocomposite sandwich constructions. Characterisation of foams in respect of their mechanical performance compared to fossil based equivalent has been conducted.

Results for the study show that the NCC-foams' mechanical properties are sufficient for composite sandwich structures. By comparing with fossil oil-based PET equivalent it is seen that when the mechanical properties are in the same region, the density of the NCC-foams is slightly higher. The intense research and development on the NCC-foam indicates that in the future it will match the oil-based PET foam on all properties.

Overall conclusion of the work is that the environmental friendly NCC-foam has potential as core material for composite sandwich structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today's society is a society in constant motion with a strong focus on rapid development. The desire for rapid development and continuous growth causes Earth's resources to be consumed in an increasingly fast pace. A race towards a more sustainable society is going on worldwide [1-4]. In order to achieve a sustainable society from a low carbon and bio-economic point of view a reduced consumption of petroleum and petroleum-based products is needed. Constituents in conventional fibre-reinforced composite sandwich structures which are widely used in marine applications, sports, aerospace and construction, such as carbon fibre, polyester, vinyl ester, epoxy resins, PVC- and PET foam are usually oil-based. It is therefore of great importance for our society that we are trying to replace these petroleum-based products with bio-based equivalents. The bio-based composites are mainly produced by renewable CO₂-neutral plants. Such materials can replace less environmentally friendly alternatives in a variety of applications; especially interesting is the use of lightweight materials in vehicles. The market for bio-based composites has grown for decades and continued growth is expected [5].

Cellulose, the primary structural component of plants, is the most ubiquitous and abundant organic compound on the planet. When cellulose fibrils are processed under carefully controlled conditions, it

is possible to release highly crystalline nano-particles known as “nano crystalline cellulose (NCC)”. NCC has some very interesting mechanical properties: a single NCC fibre typically has a Young’s modulus of around 150 GPa and a strength of 10 GPa[6].

This study addresses the by MELODEA and the Hebrew University of Jerusalem recently developed unique technique for self-assembling NCC into highly ordered layered cellular structure, i.e. foams, for use as lightweight core materials for biocomposite sandwich constructions[7,8]. Characterisation of foams in respect of its mechanical performance compared to fossil based equivalent has been conducted.

2 MATERIALS

Materials used in this study are

- AIREX® T92.100, manufactured by the Swiss company Airex AG. This foam is a closed-cell polyethylene terephthalate, PET foam with good mechanical properties and excellent price/performance ratio.
- NCC-Foams is the foam under development by Melodea.

3 MANUFACTURING OF NCC-FOAMS

Manufacturing NCC-Foams take advantage of the growth of ice crystals to template colloidal suspensions. Using the freezing of colloids (NCC in water) to template the porosity in materials is known as ice-templating or freeze-casting [9]. The basic idea is to obtain a porosity that is a replica of the ice crystals, by freezing suspension and subsequently removing the ice crystals by solvent exchange. In ice templating, the particles in suspension in the slurry are ejected from the moving solidification front and pile up between the growing columnar or lamellar ice (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ice schematic model (from <http://sylvaindeville.net/research/ice-templating-of-porous-materials/>)

These NCC scaffolds can then be used as a basis for dense composite, if infiltrated with a suitable second phase (resin). The NCC foam obtained by this process exhibit improved properties which far exceed what could be expected from a simple mixture of their components. Resin used for impregnation/strengthening is a mix of thermosetting resins.

Controlling the freezing progress and the freezing front can tailor the macro properties of the NCC-foam.

After the sample is frozen the challenge is efficient removal of the water while maintaining a stable 3D structure. In the NCC-Foam project the process was developed by solvent exchange process by placing the sample in ethanol followed by exchange to fresh ethanol and third exchange to ethanol that contains crosslinking monomers for final strengthening of the foams.

4 METHOD

4.1 Image analysis

Image analysis was done using SEM “Jeol JSM-6460LV scanning electron microscope” and sputtering of the samples was done with a “Balzers Sputter Coater SCD 050”. The magnification of the microscope goes from 5x up to 100 000x, the accelerating voltage range is 0.3 to 30 kV. It has two

electron detectors, the backscattered which work in high and low vacuum and the secondary electron detector which can only work in high vacuum conditions.

4.2 Compression test and Density measurements

Compression tests were performed according to ASTM C-365 standard [10] with sample dimensions of 50 x 50 x 10 mm. The samples were cut from four different plates (Plate 1-4) of dimension 300 x 200 x 10 mm. The number of samples from each plate was between 15 and 21. Figure 2 shows compression test specimens cut from one of the larger plates. The density was determined by recording the weight of each compression sample and divide with the volume, calculated by caliper measurement of the dimensions.

Figure 2. Compression specimen cut from one of the NCC-foam plates.

4.3 Flatwise Tensile test

Flatwise tensile tests were performed in accordance with ASTM C-297 standard [11] to determine the tensile strength of the core material. With flatwise tensile test (FWT) the uniaxial tensile force normal to the plane of the sandwich is determined. The force is transmitted to the core material via steel fixtures glued on each side of the foam. Failure modes which are not internal in the core are not acceptable, i.e. failure by debonding is not acceptable.

Figure 3 Permissible bonded assembly tolerances presented in the standard ASTM C-297

Samples were cut accomplishing the minimum facing area required for continuous bonding

surfaces of 625 mm^2 . The test specimens have a square cross-section and a thickness equal to the sandwich panel thickness. As is depicted in the standard, the specimen preparation and cutting was done with extreme care and all the samples were labelled and measured three times.

The samples were bonded to the fixtures with two component epoxy paste adhesive Araldite®. The curing was made according to supplier data sheet. The samples were placed under low pressure by placing steel plates on top during curing. The fixtures used were steel fixtures with dimensions $60 \times 50 \times 50 \text{ mm}$; thickness, length and width respectively. Meeting thus the minimum requirement of thickness of 50 mm. The load was applied to the specimens at constant rate of 0.5 mm/min.

4.4 Shear test

Characterisation of shear properties was done according to ASTM C-273 standard [12]. The test should be developed directly on the core materials bonded to the fixtures. This test provides information about the shear strength parallel to the plane of the sandwich as well as the shear modulus related to the strain in the normal plane. From the curve which relates the load versus displacement it is possible to calculate the core shear stress at any load and also the effective core shear modulus. In spite of the fact that this test does not produce pure shear it should be pointed out that due to the length of the specimen the secondary stresses have a minimum effect.

The specimens for the shear test should meet the following geometric requirements: be as thick as the thickness of the sandwich as well as to have a minimum width of 50 mm and a minimum length of twelve times the thickness. The specimen density should be calculated weighting to the nearest 0.1 g. The specimens are bonded to steel fixtures, Figure 17. Specimens were bonded using Araldite® epoxy paste adhesive and the curing was made at room temperature. Pressure was applied by putting a small weight on top of the samples during curing. The failure mode accepted in this test is pure shear failure of the core, therefore any specimen that suffer either cohesive or adhesive failure is rejected. The cross head speed was 0.5 mm/min.

Figure 4 Load line of action for shear test depicted in the standard ASTM C-273.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Microscopy

The foam cell structure is important for the mechanical properties as well as for processability of composite sandwich structures. A comprehensive characterization of the cell structure has been done in order to be able to study the processing-structure and structure-properties relations. The SEM-analysis reveals that the foam has an open-cell structure. In Figure 5 it can be observed that there is no clear regularity of the cell shape and the cell size varies. Superficially the foam cell shape seems to

consist of irregular bubbles that have collapsed during the formation. However, careful analysis reveals that some cells clearly share edge with three other cells, and have a common face with two other cells, which would imply that the tetrakaidecahedron, also known as the Kelvin cell, is the main typical cell shape of the NCC foam [13].

Figure 5. Micrograph taken from the SEM with a magnification of X95.

5.2 Compression and Density results

Compression and density results for samples from four NCC-foam plates as well as data from the material data sheet for PET T92.100 is presented in Table 1.

Foam No.	No. of 5x5 cm samples tested	Density (kg/m ³) ± Standard Error	Compressive strength (MPa)	Specific Compressive strength (kPa/(kg/m ³))
NCC 1	21	190.0 ± 1.4	1.58 ± 0.03	8.32
NCC 2	15	197.2 ± 1.6	1.60 ± 0.04	8.11
NCC 3	20	197.3 ± 1.4	1.68 ± 0.03	8.51
NCC 4	17	192.8 ± 1.5	1.68 ± 0.03	8.71
T92.100	From MDS	105 (102-112)	1.4 (1.2-1.4)	13.33

Table 1 Summary of NCC-Foams density and compressive strength results

From Table 1 it can be observed that the density of the NCC-Foam is higher than that of the PET foam and that the absolute value for the compressive strength is higher for the NCC-Foam than for the PET foam. This is somewhat a consequence of the higher density, foam properties are direct dependent on density, which can be seen comparing the specific values giving higher values for the PET foam. The compressive properties of the NCC-Foam indicate that it can be used for composite core applications. Using it in applications where higher densities are desired from a sound insulating point of view gives that it is a promising alternative to oil-based foams.

5.3 Flatwise Tensile test

The load displacement curves from flatwise tensile tests for the PET foam and the NCC foam are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 respectively. Average tensile strengths are shown in Table 2.

Figure 6. Load displacement curves obtained from the tensile test of the PET foam.

Figure 7. Load displacement curves obtained from the tensile test of the NCC foam.

From Figure 6 and Figure 7 it can be observed that the behaviour of the two types of foam is different. The failure in all PET samples, is ductile, while the failure for all the NCC foam samples is brittle.

Foam	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Specific tensile strength [kPa/(kg/m ³)]
<i>PET</i>	2.2 ±0.2	21.2
<i>NCC</i>	0.4 ±0.1	2.1

Table 2 Tensile strength for the NCC-Foam

The average tensile strength is 2.2 MPa for the PET foam while it is only 1/5 of that for the NCC foam. The strength-to-weight ratio becomes even worse due to the higher density of the NCC-Foam.

5.4 Shear test

The load displacement curves from shear tests for the PET foam and the NCC foam are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 respectively. Shear results are presented in Table 3.

Figure 8. Load displacement curves obtained from the shear test of the PET foam.

Figure 9. Load displacement curves obtained from the shear test of the NCC foam.

From Figure 8 and Figure 9 it can again be observed that the behaviour of the two types of foam is different. The failure in all PET samples, is ductile, while the failure for all the NCC foam samples is brittle.

Foam	Max Load [N]	Shear Stress [MPa]	Specific shear stress [Pa/(kg/m ³)]	Shear Modulus [MPa]	Specific shear modulus [kPa/(kg/m ³)]
<i>PET</i>	8039 ±557	1.0 ±0.1	9.3 ±0.7	8.6 ±0.5	83.6±4.9
<i>NCC</i>	2954 ±632	0.3 ±0.1	1.7 ±0.3	8.9 ±0.9	46.6±4.4

Table 3 Shear test results

From the shear test results, Table 3, it can be observed that the maximum load for the NCC-foam is less than half of that for PET foam while the modulus of the two different foam types are in the same range.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A novel bio-based foam based on Nano Crystalline Cellulose, NCC-Foam, is under development. Its structure has been studied and its properties have been compared to fossil oil based PET foam in terms of density, compression, tension and shear properties. The foam structure is an open cell structure of Kelvin cell type. The average density of the NCC-foam is found to be 190 kg/m³, the PET foam used for comparison has an average density of 105 kg/m³. It is observed that the tensile- and shear strength of the NCC-foam is lower than that of the PET foam. The shear modulus of the both materials are nearly identical. Furthermore it can be observed that the NCC-foam exhibit a brittle behaviour while the PET foam is more ductile.

The results for the NCC-foam show that the properties are high enough to be used as a composite sandwich core for specific applications. The higher density can be an advantage when other properties like sound insulation are more important than weight. Further development of the foam by Melodea will be carried out during the duration of the NCC-FOAM project.

The rapid development and intense research on processing-structure and structure properties of the NCC-foam gives great expectations that in the future its properties will be possible to tailor for targeted applications.

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